

The Main Flows of Female Labor Migration

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Abstract: This article describes the causes and factors of female labor migration, analyzes the number and proportion of female labor migrants in the countries of the world, and presents the main trends and modern directions of female labor migration.

Keywords: female labor migration, feminization, transformation, unemployment, poverty, debt, lack of housing, poverty, economic reasons.

Introduction. One of the modern features of international labor migration is its feminization. Structural changes in the world economy, such as the development of industries that do not require heavy physical labor, in particular, the service sector, and the transformation of the employment structure, in particular, the development of the service sector, gave impetus to the formation and development of female labor migration, which has become an important part of the global labor migration. In addition to such a transformation in the structure of employment, a decrease in the birth rate and an increase in the average life expectancy of people in developed countries lead to an increase in the number of elderly people and their caregivers, an improvement in the material well-being of the population of this country and an increase in the participation of women in society and domestic workers have led to an increase in demand.

In addition to economic reasons, such as unemployment, poverty, debt, lack of housing, need, social factors, such as family disagreements, divorces, women's desire for education and development of themselves and their children, also lead to this direction of migration. While women's labor migration creates positive opportunities for its participants, such as earning income and solving economic problems, as well as professional growth, it also creates opportunities for them to become victims of human trafficking, sexual violence, discrimination and humiliation.

Main part. With the development of female labor migration, the number of single-parent or orphan families in donor countries increases, the number of elderly people whose children need care, the birth rate and the number of family formations decrease, and sometimes women's confidence in the dignity of migrants and respect for them weakens. This leads to the emergence of social problems with negative consequences and increased social pressure in the country to solve the economic problems in these countries.

In this regard, the researcher O.P. Koshulko says that if female labor migration, on the one hand, in the short term enables women to provide a quality education to their children and improve their material well-being, then, on the other hand, leads to the loss of opportunities for personal and professional growth in the long term [2]. The moral obsolescence of professional skills over time and the lack of investment in its development lead to the loss of human capital.

Like labor migration, female migration can be of legal, semi-legal and illegal forms. The legal migration of women is low, which allows them to legally enter the host country, stay there and work

under an official contract with the guards. Illegal migration of women, which has a relatively large volume and is considered particularly dangerous, is formed by short-term tourist visas and / or migrant women who entered the host country illegally and are forced to work in legal or semi-legal industries, depending on the decision of the employer. Because of this, they often become victims of discrimination, humiliation and violence. The semi-legal labor migration of women is also a large-scale and high-risk route, where they are often promised formal employment in the host country before they leave their home country, but as soon as they cross the border of the country, their identity documents are taken away, as a result, they become victims of human trafficking.

Several factors influence the development of female labor migration. According to the analysis, 40% of labor migration from Russia to Kyrgyzstan and about 20% to Tajikistan and Uzbekistan is female labor migration [3]. At the same time, researchers note that the number of persons occupying a relatively high position among them is also increasing [4]. According to N. Richikhina, the desire to have the necessary level of education, move up the career ladder, have equal rights and be independent serves to increase the number of women working in international companies [5]. Scientists M. Sekach and S. Mostikov emphasized that psychological factors related to women's belief in their own strength and the desire to lead an independent life play an important role in this regard [6].

Research shows that the reasons for women's labor migration vary across countries. For example, for women migrants from Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan, factors such as earnings, family and personal life, and for women migrants from Bashkortostan - education and upbringing of children, housing, getting rid of debts, situations such as receiving income for medical treatment loved ones motivate them to go to another country and work [7]. According to the results of empirical studies, 84% of respondents stated that labor migration of women has a positive impact on their lives and careers, and 62.4% of respondents stated that this process has a positive impact on host countries and regions [8]. As of 2021, the number of migrants in the world is 281 million people, of which 48%, i.e. 135 million, are female migrants. There are 169 million labor migrants in the world, of which 41.5%, i.e. 70.1 million, are women [9].

The level of development of countries has a significant impact on the share of female migrants. In particular, the share of female migrants increased from 49.6% to 49.8% in low-income countries, from 48.3% to 45.6% in middle-income countries, and from 48.7% to 42.8% in upper middle income countries. 69.7% of female migrant workers work in high income countries, 19.2% in upper middle income, 8.3% in lower middle income and 2.8% in low income.

Women migrants make up 5% of all workers, 18% of them work in high-income countries, 2.3% in high-income countries, 1.5% in low-income countries and 1.4% in countries with low income [11].

Female migrants of this age make up 3.8% of the total population over 15 and 5% of all workers. Migrant women make up 63.5% of the total female labor force. Specifically, the rate is 67.8% in high-income countries, 64.8% in high-income countries, 43.1% in low-middle income countries, and 48.7% in low-income countries.

Migrant women mainly work in social sectors such as household services, agriculture, hospitality, health care and education. For example, in Europe they work mainly in the health and social sectors. In particular, there is a high proportion of female migrants in the hotel business in Spain and Greece, in the field of medicine in the UK, and in education in Italy. If we look at the regional distribution of tertiary-educated migrant women of working age, we can see that their level of education is higher in high-income countries [13]. However, among female migrant workers in foreign countries, along with those working in the areas of medium and high qualifications, informal housekeepers, nannies, caregivers for the elderly, remain completely dependent on the employer in low-skilled jobs, most of them work.

Table 4 Percentage of female migrants working in the simplest occupations, by region

Countries	The lowest rate		The highest score	
High income countries	Japan	8,1%	Saudi Arabia	74%
Middle income countries	Mongolia	2,4%	Lebanon	88%
Low income countries	Guinea	2%	Costa Rica	45%

Source: Who are the women on the move? A portrait of female migrant workers//Who are the women on the move? A portrait of female migrant workers - ILOSTAT

Migrant domestic workers make up 8-9% of the world's 196 million migrant workers. If we look at this figure among migrant women, about 12% of the 70 million migrant women in the world, that is, 8.45 million, are migrant women working as domestic workers. Of the 67.2 million domestic workers worldwide, 17.2% or 11.5 million are migrant domestic workers. This testifies to the high demand of migrants for personal and domestic services around the world.

The Arab region has the highest proportion of female migrant domestic workers among the total number of migrants in the regions of the world (60.8%), while the Eastern European region has the lowest (0.8%) [14]. In the Arab region, 82% of all domestic workers are female migrants. This situation is an inextricable link between domestic workers and female migration, with the result that 6 out of 10 working women are domestic workers. Southeast Asia and East Asia are the largest sending regions for migrant women working as domestic workers. In particular, migrant women from the region work as domestic workers in the Middle East and Europe, as well as in newly industrialized countries.

According to statistics, there are 11.5 million migrant domestic workers in the world, most of them women [15]. The Middle East is the region that attracts the most migrant women from low-income countries such as Africa and Asia [16]. The fact that the majority of these female migrants are low-skilled and educated and do not know where they are going to work creates opportunities for employers to exploit various forms of exploitation such as under wages, overtime, physical force and harassment [17]. Compared to local workers, the lack of safe working conditions for migrant women working as domestic workers, physical and sexual abuse against them, violation of their rights lead to physical and mental injuries of these migrant women or to lifelong illnesses [18].

Conclusion. In conclusion, in most lower-middle and low-income countries, migrant women continue to face problems such as discrimination in the labor market, exploitation and violence at work, barriers to access to health care and education, and unfair justice.

The share of women among the victims of human trafficking is still high. In particular, 65% of victims of human trafficking are women, 46% are adults, and 19% are girls. Most adult female victims are in Europe, North America and Asia, while female victims are more common in Asia.

The above cases once again show that the problem of female labor migration remains a topical issue on the agenda and international and regional cooperation is important in preventing problems associated with this process.

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